

Evaluation and optimization of Big Data processing in Cloud Computing

Ledia Bozo

Informatics Department
Faculty of Natural Sciences
University of Tirana, Albania

Fatime Toçi

Informatics Department
Faculty of Natural Sciences
University of Tirana, Albania

Abstract—There is an increasing demand for processing tremendous volumes of data, which promotes the research on systems and techniques to optimize Big Data processing time. Traditional Systems do not offer the required flexibility, scalability and they are often inefficient in processing complex analytical tasks in finite and allowable time and scalable storage to accommodate the growing data.

In this paper, we propose a system that improves Big Data processing by implementing a MapReduce program, two Cloud Services and several optimization techniques. The system is implemented in Cloud Computing using Cloud Big Data Platform and compares several frameworks such as Hadoop, Apache Spark, HBase etc. Cloud Computing offers a complete and efficient infrastructure, powerful, scalable, and especially infinite resources during high seasonal demands.

The evaluations turn out that the proposed system has more accurate results and the processing time is improved up to 85 times faster than the Traditional System.

Keywords: *Big data, MapReduce, data processing, Cloud Computing.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays our society is generating tremendous quantities of data. This is due to the growth of internet and communication, smart devices, mobile data traffic, social media etc. According to Forbes, there are over 2.5 quintillion bytes of data generated every day. If we go back two years ago 90 percent of the data was not generated [1].

The large volume of data coming intensively from various sources and in different types that needs to be processed and analyzed introduced a new era in data management. There are several definitions for Big Data, Gartner Inc., defines it as high-volume, high-velocity and/or high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information

processing that enable enhanced insight, decision making, and process automation [2].

Big Data has attracted a lot of attention from academia as well as industry, as it offers significant value to them. Analyzing Big Data can help the industry to be more efficient, do better marketing for new services or products, be closer to the customers, and make better decisions at the right time. Studies show a positive and significant relationship between BDA and firm productivity, suggesting that live BDA assets are associated with a 4.1% increase in firm productivity [3]. According to Statista, the global big data and business analytics market was valued at 168.8 billion U.S. dollars in 2018 and is forecast to grow to 274.3 billion U.S. dollars by 2022, with a five-year compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.2 percent [4].

However, the exponential growth of data in recent years has introduced several challenges on existing infrastructure such as high processing ability to run complex analytical tasks in finite and allowable time and scalable storage that can accommodate the growing data [5]. To resolve these issues, Big Data Analytics is developed, wherein several big data tools, techniques and methodologies are acquired by organizations for extracting the right data from huge sets of unstructured data [6].

In this paper we present a system that processes big data in a considerable time. The system is optimized in Cloud Computing using Cloud Big Data Platform and several tools such as Hadoop, Apache Spark etc. The evaluations turn out that the processing time is optimized from approximately an hour to seconds.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several researches dealing with Big Data management. Anju and Shyma [7] studied various clustering methods using the map-reduce framework in big data analytics. Clustering was done on encrypted partitioned data and is focused on securing and maintaining the efficiency and performance of millions of datasets with variety, velocity, and volume.

The authors in [8] have presented the results of an experimental study on the performance of Spark with the most

popular databases of NoSQL MongoDB and Hadoop. The objective of this study is to determine the software combination that allows sophisticated analysis of Big Data.

[9] provides a comparative study of four of the most common big data processing frameworks include Apache Hadoop, Apache Spark, Apache Storm, and Apache Flink. It summarizes key performance indicators, which are processing time, CPU consumption, latency, throughput, execution time etc.

Work presented in [10] concerns a cloudlet based healthcare and medical knowledge extraction system for medical Big Data. The paper proposes a system to provide confidentiality of medical information and protect the healthcare system from intrusion.

If we have a glance at data processing in Hadoop, [11] is focused on improving performance for analyzing social networks. This is achieved by comparing the relative performance of Solid-State Drives (SSDs) versus hard disk drives (HDDs) when they are used as underlying storage for Hadoop's MapReduce. As a result, this paper provides that future studies must not blindly add SSDs to Hadoop, but is important to build components for assessing the type of processing pattern of the application and then direct the data to the appropriate storage medium.

The authors in [12] analyze all the reasons for the small file problem of HDFS. In the context of HDFS, the clear cut-off point between large and small files is determined through experimentation, which helps determine the most optimized file size. The paper proposes an optimized approach to improve the storage and access efficiencies of small files.

III. CASE STUDY

In this paper we will illustrate a real-life system from industry processing Big Data, the problems, and challenges that this system has faced and the proposed solution.

A. Existing System

The company has built a private Cloud and has implemented a system that consists of three main parts, such as:

- The core system that deals with technical processing.
- Middleware system that is responsible for business logic and
- Content Management System.

The Middleware System gets approximately 10 GB of customer logs every day. The Company is very interested in analyzing customer behavior to make better decisions about the products and services offered for the customers. Since the information is very valuable, Splunk is used to process the data and generate necessary reports and statistics for the company as illustrated below in figure 1.

Figure 1. Architecture of existing system

Since generating the reports real-time takes nearly an hour, data is preprocessed at night hours, consequently the company analyzes the reports one day later. On the other hand, the company expects additional growth of customer data, which leads to more efforts for better management to get quick results. The company needs a solution for two problems:

- a) Validating data to have accurate results.
- b) Analyzing Big Data efficiently to reduce dramatically the processing time to respond to the marketplace immediately.

B. Proposed System

We propose a new management of customer logs, to optimize the processing time in the Cloud as described in figure 2.

First, we propose a Preprocess service to increase Big Data quality and prepare for the processing phase with accurate data. The service will help the management of complexity, aggregating various sources of data together, cleaning up all unnecessary data and applying specific conditions in order to filter unwanted information, therefore the process analyses less information and the results are more accurate.

Second, a Smart service is proposed to help optimization procedures. It determines maximum file size and applies specific data compression.

Next, the data will be processed in parallel using a map-reduce programming model on an AWS EMR Cluster. Hadoop allows clustering multiple computers to analyze enormous datasets in parallel more quickly and Cloud offers the ability to expand and shrink the running cluster on demand to provide the best processing time.

Figure 2. Proposed System

Finally, we will use several optimization techniques from optimizing the map-reduce algorithm to the optimization of every step of the process to achieve the desired result.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Map-Reduce Programming Model

MapReduce is a programming model [13] for easily processing large amounts of data in parallel, executed on large clusters in a reliable manner. It consists of two main parts, mapper and reducer. Mapper takes the data and converts it into another set of data, where individual elements are broken down into chunks of data, in the form of key/value pairs. Then there is an intermediate phase (shuffling) when the output of the mapping function is grouped by keys and redistributed in a way that all data with the same key are located on the same node. Reducer is performed after shuffling, taking the output as an input, and combining those data chunks into a smaller set of tuples.

B. Map-Reduce Algorithm

The algorithm intertwines two powerful mechanisms: MapReduce & Pandas. Pandas Library works through “dataframes”, the main object of every operation, in which it can store huge amounts of data, from various formats, manipulating and organizing the data in the way we want. It reduces the time of algorithm execution by applying its one-line solutions for retrieving columns required, changing the columns format, grouping, and aggregating all the data frames based on the desired output [14].

The algorithm is developed in Python and applies the MapReduce technique by separating the code into two blocks:

- Mapper, into which the data is being processed and mapped into several chunks of data by retrieving only the information needed for the final output.

- Reducer, into which the data coming from the mapper is being processed and prepared for the final output.

Algorithm 1

Mapper:

Create a Dataset

for all elements in Dataset do

if condition 1 and condition 2 are met then

retrieve parameter 1, parameter 2, parameter 3 in list

end if

end for

Reducer:

for all elements in list do

group by parameter 1 and sum parameter 2, parameter 3

end for

The Algorithm is simple and is implemented to be used in general cases. It uses Parameter 1 as Key and Parameter 2 Parameter 3 as Values. Mapper and reducer are correct and functional, but there are opportunities for improvement.

C. Improved Algorithm

There are several approaches for improvement:

- We need a service to clean up unnecessary data, since not all the data is needed to be processed. Preprocess Service is implemented to filter the data before loading.
 - It is important to keep the algorithm as simple as possible excluding data conversions and conditions. Necessary conditions will be implemented in Preprocess Service.
 - Use a Dataframe, dictionary, parallelized structures of Pandas and reuse existing objects to improve performance.
 - Make the algorithm more general to be applied in every request of the case study.
-

Preprocess Service

Emits unnecessary data to be loaded based on specified conditions.

Algorithm 2

Mapper:

Create a Dataframe

Retrieve columns parameter 1... parameter N in Dictionary

Reducer:

for all elements in Dictionary do

sum parameter2 ... parameter N

end for

D. Final Optimizations

We need to experiment further optimizations to get best results:

- Initializing map-reduce tasks is costly. As the authors in [12] suggest, file size is important in algorithm performance. We need a Smart Service to aggregate data from different sources and match them up to a variable maximum file size. The Service will be responsible to determine continuously the value of the variable optimal file size.
- We compress the data by Smart Service using LZ0 compression to reduce the amount of storage needed for the data and minimize the network traffic between S3 and the EMR nodes.
- Reading and writing to the disk is time expensive. We will experiment with the usage of Cluster Distributed In-Memory Caching. Each Cache Cluster is a collection of Cache Nodes and each cluster resides in a particular AWS Availability Zone. Cache Cluster is a distributed, in-memory cache that can be accessed using the popular Memcached protocol [15].
- Cluster configuration is very important in the whole process performance. We will experiment several cluster configurations in terms of instance size, instance type, number of instances and instance lifetime to have the best performance and a reasonable cost.
- We will try AWS auto scaling and several frameworks such as Hadoop, Spark and HBase to test the best performance of map-reduce algorithms.

V. EVALUATIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

To validate the proposed architecture, we will compare the traditional system's performance with the proposed system deployed in Amazon's AWS services.

The traditional system implemented in the private Cloud has an infrastructure of 16 virtual 3GHz processors and 24GB RAM. We have tested the existing system in three different days, and we got these results:

TABLE I. EXISTING SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

Splunk	Performance Evaluation in seconds		
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Execution	3032.77 sec	3283.77 sec	3083.61sec

We implemented and configured the proposed system using the first map-reduce algorithm and the improved algorithm responsible for processing 9.7 GB of data. The total time required for the execution of the proposed system is evaluated in several frameworks: Hadoop, Hadoop with auto scaling from 2 instances to 5 instances, Spark and HBase with auto scaling from minimum 2 instances to 5 instances. The best instance type results regarding performance and cost is "m5.xlarge" that consists of 4 virtual CPUs and 16 GB RAM. Figure 3 shows the performance evaluation of the first map-reduce algorithm and the improved one in AWS EMR Cluster.

Figure 2. Map-Reduce Algorithms Performance in AWS EMR Cluster

The evaluation of the algorithms shows that the best performance is 585 seconds that corresponds to the improved algorithm in Spark framework. Figure 4 compares the best performance of the Traditional System with the best performance of map-reduce algorithm in AWS EMR Cluster.

Figure 3. Map-Reduce Algorithm versus Tradition System

There is a big difference between the improved map-reduce algorithm performance and traditional system. We have made the process of customer data more than five times faster, but we cannot get the required reports real-time. It takes approximately ten minutes to process all the customer data.

Finally, we implemented the whole optimized system, deploying two services Preprocessed Service and Smart Service as described in figure 2. We applied all the techniques discussed in methodology and final optimizations and after several experiments the proposed system showed best performance using “m5.xlarge” instance type without scaling and using distributed cluster cache. Figure 5 shows the excellent results:

Figure 4. Performance of Proposed System by Cluster Instance Type

Experiments confirmed that the proposed system performed faster with a maximum file size of 10 GB evaluated by Smart Service. The best execution time is 35.73 seconds in “m5.xlarge” instance cluster with a reasonable cost. The Optimized System is 85 times faster than the Traditional System providing us real time calculations using AWS EMR Cluster infrastructure.

The system is monitored continuously and will release not used resources in not working hours and weekends to save costs.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we proposed a new management of customer logs, to optimize the processing time using MapReduce program and Cloud Services. The primary advantage of this system is having more accurate results and managing the complexity of different data sources in an efficient way.

The Cloud Services have a significant role in a better analysis of Big Data Processing. The Preprocessed Service is responsible to clean up and filter by applying certain conditions that exclude unwanted data from loading to Cloud Cluster. The system implemented a Smart Service to calculate maximum file size and aggregate data from different sources in performant format ready to be processed by a MapReduce algorithm.

We observed that the program execution time was reduced when using the improved MapReduce program and improved significantly when compared with the existing system. Significant improvements are made by managing cluster configuration, using Cluster Distributed Cache, Spark framework and of course data compression to reduce data transport and manipulation in the Cloud.

We got excellent results during system evaluation. The proposed systems perform 85 faster than the Tradition one executing 10 GB of data from approximately one hour to 35.73 seconds.

REFERENCES

- [1] Marr B., Forbes: How Much Data Do We Create Every Day? The Mind-Blowing Stats Everyone Should Read, 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2018/05/21/how-much-data-do-we-create-every-day-the-mind-blowing-stats-everyone-should-read/#481a06c960ba>.
- [2] Gartner IT Glossary (n.d.). 2020, Retrieved from <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/big-data/>
- [3] Müller, O., Fay, M., vom Brocke, J. (2018) The Effect of Big Data and Analytics on Firm Performance: An Econometric Analysis Considering Industry Characteristics, *Journal of Management Information Systems* 10.1080/07421222.2018.1451955, pp 22.
- [4] Holst A., Statista: Big data and business analytics revenue worldwide 2015-2022, 2020, Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/551501/worldwide-big-data-business-analytics-revenue/>
- [5] Khan S., Shakil A. K., Alam M. (2017) Big Data Computing Using Cloud-Based Technologies: Challenges and Future Perspectives, Chapman and Hall/CRC, 1712.05233, pp 2-3
- [6] Madaan A., Sharma V., Pahwa P., Das P., Sharma C. (2018) Hadoop: Solution to Unstructured Data Handling. *Big Data Analytics. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 654. Springer, Singapore: 978-981-10-6620-7_6
- [7] Anju Abraham, and Shyma Kareem., 2018, "Security and Clustering Of Big Data in Map Reduce Framework "International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas And Innovations In Technology Volume 4, Issue 1,pp-199, ISSN:2454-132X
- [8] Hajoui, Omar & Talea, Mohamed. (2018). Which NoSQL Database to Combine with Spark for Real Time Big Data Analytics ?. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*, Vol.16.
- [9] Alkatheri, Safaa & Abbas, Samah & Siddiqui, Muazzam. (2019). A Comparative Study of Big Data Frameworks. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*, Vol. 17.
- [10] Chandavale A. A., Grade A. (2018). Cloudlet based Healthcare and Medical KnowledgeExtraction System for Medical Big Data. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*, Vol. 16. (pp. 146-152)
- [11] Bakratsas, Marios & Basaras, Pavlos & Katsaros, D. & Tassioulas, L., (2017). Hadoop MapReduce Performance on SSDs for Analyzing Social Networks. *Big Data Research*. 11. 10.1016/j.bdr.2017.06.001.
- [12] Dong, B., Zheng, Q., Tian, F., Chao, K., Ma, R., & Anane, R. (2012). An optimized approach for storing and accessing small files on cloud storage. *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, 35, 1847-1862.
- [13] Dean, J.; Ghemawat, S. MapReduce: Simplified data processing on large clusters. *Commun. ACM* 2008, 51, 107–113.
- [14] Pandas Documentation 2020, Retrieved from <https://pandas.pydata.org/docs/>.
- [15] Amazon EC2, 2020, Retrieved from <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/aws/amazon-elasticache-distributed-in-memory-caching/>